
Review

Exploring Customer Loyalty in the Digital Gaming Sphere: A Case Study on Tencent Games

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Abstract: This review article delves into the competitive and dynamic world of mobile gaming, with a particular focus on Tencent, China's preeminent force in mobile games, social networking services, and online payment systems. As the largest provider of mobile games in China, Tencent navigates a fiercely competitive landscape, not only from local giants like Baidu and Alibaba but also from an ever-evolving array of startups. This competition underscores a market where execution and rapid response to consumer demands are paramount, overshadowing the mere novelty of ideas.

The explosion of mobile gaming into mainstream consumer culture has transformed it into a daily activity for millions, driven by a diversity of platforms, gaming needs, and business models, notably the free-to-play model. This shift raises pertinent questions about player engagement, loyalty, and the reasons behind the widespread adoption of certain games over others. Despite extensive research in this field, the literature remains fragmented, necessitating a comprehensive review to consolidate our understanding of these dynamics.

Historically, many mobile game developers have faltered by neglecting customer needs—a critical aspect that Tencent's "Honour of Kings" seems to have mastered, leading to its popularity in China. The review emphasizes the importance of customer-centric strategies in achieving success in the online gaming industry. It stresses that understanding and innovating according to the gamers' needs are non-negotiable prerequisites for sustainability and growth in the mobile gaming sector.

Furthermore, the review highlights the pivotal role of analytics in the mobile gaming industry, where every player interaction is meticulously analyzed to refine games, enhance user engagement, and optimize monetization strategies. In a market dominated by a few major publishers, understanding the factors influencing purchase intentions and player loyalty becomes crucial for survival and growth.

This comprehensive review aims to synthesize existing research on player engagement and loyalty in mobile gaming, with a special emphasis on the strategic maneuvers of Tencent amidst China's highly competitive digital landscape. It seeks to unravel the complexities behind what drives player loyalty and engagement in a market where customer satisfaction is the key to enduring success.

Keywords: Mobile game, Customer Loyalty, User Satisfaction, Tencent Games.

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Introduction

Tencent is the largest mobile games provider in China with a wide range of game types, China's largest social networking service provider with several of the largest social networking applications in the world, and China's favorite Internet portal. It was challenging Alibaba's Alipay as the leader in online payments systems, and it had established strategic relationships with many service providers to help exploit new opportunities in online-to-offline (O2O) services and leverage its huge user base in e-commerce and search. However, there was no room for complacency. Competition from the other big local Internet companies such as Baidu and Alibaba was fierce, and there were always thousands of start-ups looking to enter the sector. Founder and CEO Ma Huateng ("Pony" Ma) remarked, "In America, when you bring an idea to market you usually have several months before competition pops up, allowing you to capture significant market share. In China, you can have hundreds of competitors within the first hours of going live. Ideas are not important in China-execution is."

During the last, mobile games have become an established vein of entertainment, consumer culture, and essentially, a common part of people's daily lives. With the increased penetration of games, also the ways in which people play and employ games have become more varied. The long-tail is getting longer. There are more different kinds of games available for a multitude of different platforms that cater to different gaming needs for widening audiences and which use a wide variety of business models. Especially the free-to-play revenue model which enables developers to offer major parts of the game for free has further fed into this development. Due to this divergence, questions such as why people play games are especially timely. Even though the topic has been studied widely, the current body of literature seems scattered. It is important to look back and review what we currently know about why people adopt games, keep playing them and what makes people loyal to certain games. The purpose of this study is to review past literature pertaining to these aspects.

There has been done a lot of study on this regard but in almost every study reveal that this is done due to neglecting the customers which is the prime concern of digital gaming. According to the survey, "Honour of Kings" from Tencent is the most popular game in China, followed by League of Legends. There is a study made on online gaming reveals that the main reason for not becoming successful in online gaming is not understanding the gamer's needs very well or not understanding the gamers' need properly and efficiently. If a mobile game company wants to be successful then they must understand the customers need very well and provide continuously innovative products (Kristensen & Westlund, Accountable business performance measurement for sustainable business excellence, 2004). Without doing this mobile game company can't be successful, so a mobile game company must be customer oriented. Most of the mobile game companies are now concerned about the issue so it is expected that customers may get a quality service from the games.

Mobile game publishing in 2018 is highly reactive. From lots of articles, we could clearly see the Mobile Game market growth in a good momentum and broad prospects. It also has a huge potential to increase. Few industries in the world are quite as focused on analytics as mobile gaming. Every in-game action, every download, micro-purchase, and social share is scrutinized. Unlikely the traditional PC game, Mobile Game allow the user playing anywhere, anytime and even walking and playing. As long as the hardware design and network quality develop extremely fast, there is no

much constraint to stop the mobile game become the dominant power in the visual game market. Mobile gaming's revenues are now dominated by a very small number of publishing companies that fill their hoppers with "category" games and then watch consumer reaction, like hungry hawks gazing down at worms in a jar. The monetization models, the games themselves, the marketing, are all tweaked according to the consumer's minutest reactions. In order to survive in this highly competitive market environment, the key factor will be understood what will affect the customer's purchase intention. Because many research papers point out the most important things could influence the customer making the buying decision is purchase intention. Finally, under this background, this thesis will focus on which factors could influence the purchase intention when customers buy the mobile game. I believe it has significant meaning for the game companies and related fields.

1.1.1 Company Background

Tencent Holdings Limited (Chinese: 腾讯控股有限公司; pinyin: Téngxùn Kònggǔ Yǒuxiàn Gōngsī) is a Chinese worldwide venture holding combination established in 1998, whose backups have some expertise in different Internet-related administrations and items, stimulation, man-made brainpower, and innovation both in China and all around. Its twin-high raises home office Tencent Seafront Towers (otherwise called Tencent Binhai Mansion) is situated in Shenzhen.

Tencent is the world's biggest gaming organization, one of the world's most significant innovation aggregates, one of the world's biggest web-based social networking organizations, and one of the world's biggest funding firms and venture companies. Its numerous administrations incorporate informal organization, music, web-based interfaces, web-based business, portable amusements, web administrations, installment frameworks, cell phones, and multiplayer internet recreations, which are all among the world's greatest and best in their separate classes. Contributions in China incorporate the moment delivery person Tencent QQ and one of the biggest web-based interfaces, QQ.com. It likewise claims most of China's music administrations (Tencent Music Entertainment), with in excess of 700 million dynamic clients and 120 million paying supporters. The organization outperformed the market estimation of US\$500 billion of every 2018, turning into the main Asian innovation organization to cross the valuation mark. It was from that point forward developed as a standout amongst Asia's most important organizations, and among the world's best innovation organizations by market esteem. Tencent has been credited as one of the world's most creative organizations by various media and firms, including Boston Consulting Group. Starting in 2018, Tencent is the fifth highest global brand.

Tencent controls many auxiliaries and partners in various ventures and regions, making an expansive arrangement of possessions and speculation over an assorted scope of organizations including online business, retail, video gaming, land, programming, augmented reality, ride-sharing, banking, monetary administrations, fintech, purchaser innovation, PC innovation, car, film generation, motion picture ticketing, music creation, space innovation, regular assets, cell phones, enormous information, horticulture, restorative administrations, distributed computing, web-based life, IT, publicizing, spilling media, computerized reasoning, apply autonomy, UAVs, sustenance conveyance, dispatch administrations, digital book, web administrations, instruction, and sustainable power source. It is a standout amongst the most dynamic and fruitful venture enterprises on the planet, with stakes in more than 600 organizations, and ongoing spotlight on new businesses inside Asia's thriving tech scene.

Tencent Games:

Tencent Games (Chinese: 腾讯游戏; pinyin: Téngxùn Yóuxì) is the computer game distributing division of Tencent Interactive Entertainment, itself a division of Tencent. Tencent Games was established in 2003 to concentrate on web-based diversions. Tencent discharged its first amusement QQ Tang (QQ 堂) in 2004, which is based off its internet-based life stage QQ. This was before long pursued by QQ variation amusements, for example, Dungeon Fighter Online, a side-looking over online beat them up diversion; QQ Fantasy, a 2D internet diversion that fuses components from Chinese folklore; Xunxian, a 3D, online RPG; QQ Sanguo, an online easygoing pretending diversion set amid the authentic three kingdoms time frame; QQ Huaxia, an online RPG; QQ Dancer, an online melodic moving amusement that offers QQ

IM intelligence; QQ Nanaimo, a web-based amusement set on a desert island where players keep up houses and pets; QQ Speed, an easygoing web-based hustling diversion; QQ R2Beat, an online in-line skating amusement; QQ Tang, a "progressed easygoing amusement" with ongoing interaction got from Chinese writing; QQ PET, and a QQ IM-based work area virtual pet game.[In 2015, Tencent discharged its multiplayer online fight field amusement Honor of Kings (王者荣耀) only for the Chinese market, and by 2017 was both the world's most prominent and most astounding netting round ever just as the most downloaded application comprehensively. Tencent likewise discharged a global form of Honor of Kings named Arena of Valor in 2017. For the event of the nineteenth National Party Congress, Tencent discharged a versatile diversion titled "Applaud Xi Jinping: An Awesome Speech", in which players have 19 seconds to create however many applauds as could be expected under the circumstances for Xi.

In 2011, Tencent began facilitating enormously multiplayer web-based amusements, for example, Call of Duty Online, comprising of past Call of Duty titles with included substance, just as the diversion League of Legends, of which now it completely possesses. Tencent likewise halfway possesses fight royale amusements, for example, Fortnite and Player Unknown's Battlegrounds, and completely claims Ring of Elysium. Beginning in 2016, Tencent built up a video gaming console named TGP (Tencent Gaming Platform) Box. The TGP BOX is known as the Blade. It is an Intel-fueled reassure running Windows 10 and a TGP Box mode. Up until this point, the TGP comfort has imported numerous Tencent amusements, for example, League of Legends, FIFA Online 3, NBA 2K, Monster Hunter, Need for Speed, and Player Unknown's Battlegrounds. Tencent wants to bring outsider created recreations. In April 2017, Tencent divulged its own lead gaming stage, WeGame which will have recreations, substance, and administrations from everywhere throughout the world and will give gaming information, buys, downloads, live gushing and network administrations, making an open biological system for gaming. WeGame is a redesigned variant of TGP (Tencent Games Platform) that as of now has in excess of 200 million dynamic clients (contrasted with Steam's 125 million) and over 4.5 billion downloads, and is broadly considered as an immediate contender to Steam. It will be committed to both worldwide designers and players and will help engineers who require help with interpretation. The gaming stage will bolster both Chinese and worldwide clients through a solitary customer facing facade and is expected to go online on 1 September 2017, Tencent has expressed that the stage will concentrate on PC and independent amusements and will never again have web or portable recreations, and will offer help to little and outside the box organizations. Beside standard amusements, the organization has guaranteed to likewise dispatch titles which incorporate Stardew Valley, Rocket League, Portal Knights, Minecraft, Cities: Skylines, with 170 recreations guaranteed before the finish of 2017. There are desires that WeGame will become tremendous and fruitful universally with its new spotlight on Western clients, joined with the gigantic purchasing intensity of the present Asian buyers.

As of March 2018, Tencent is the biggest computer game organization on the planet. Tencent lion's share claims amusement organizations Grinding Gear Games (80%), Miniclip (undisclosed dominant part stake), Riot Games (100%) and Supercell (84.3%).

1.1.3 Glory of kings' game review

Wangzhe Rongyao (Chinese: 王者荣耀; pinyin: Wángzhě Róngyào, fluidly referred to in English unofficial interpretations as Honor of Kings, King of Glory, Kings of Glory, Honor of King, or Honor of King, and on the other hand transliterated as Wang Zhe Rong Yao) is a multiplayer online fight field created and distributed by Tencent Games for the iOS and Android versatile platforms, solely for the Chinese market. By 2017, Wangzhe Rongyao has had more than 80 million day by day dynamic players and 200 million month to month dynamic players and was both the world's most prevalent and most astounding earning round ever just as the most downloaded application globally. The diversion's worldwide adaptation has been discharged in 2017 as Arena of Valor, highlighting distinctive substance.

1.1.4 Historical Background

In 2015, Tencent moved toward Riot Games and requested that they transform their prevalent amusement League of Legends into a portable title. In any case, Riot declined and asserted that League of Legends' ongoing interaction

couldn't be duplicated on cell phones. Tencent at that point went before to make their own portable diversion, Wangzhe Rongyao generally meant English as Honor of Kings. The diversion got a beta discharge for iOS and Android platforms on November 26, 2015. Notwithstanding a player versus condition (PvE) parker mode, running mode, the diversion highlights player versus player (PvP) multiplayer fights. The diversion highlights numerous likenesses to League of Legends. In November 2016, Wangzhe Rongyao topped the 2016 China container diversion celebration "China IP file esteem list - amusement list top10". In 2016, the amusement had more than 50 million day by day dynamic clients and more than 200 million enlisted clients. The diversion earned ¥10.4 billion (\$1.61 billion) in the last quarter of 2016. In May 2017, it turned into the most elevated earning versatile diversion in the world It had 160 million month to month dynamic clients. In May 2017, performer Lu Han was named ambassador of the diversion. According to an examiner at BOC International, Wangzhe Rongyao will contribute about half of the Tencent's versatile gaming incomes in 2017 and it made around 3 billion Yuan in gross income in April 2017 (\$435 million). In June 2017, the examination organization APP Annie reported that Wangzhe Rongyao was the number 1 portable amusement (barring Android diversions) in the world as far as pay age, with first-quarter income of the diversion coming to \$1.76 billion. A saint skin of Zhao Yun likewise had sold for \$22 million out of one day. At the time, Tencent reported 200 million enlisted clients with 50 million day by day dynamic clients. The diversion earned \$911 million in the second quarter of 2017. Between the last quarter of 2016 and the second quarter of 2017, the diversion earned \$4.281 billion. In September 2017, Nintendo reported an arrangement with Tencent to convey Wangzhe Rongyao to the Nintendo Switch as Arena of Valor for universal markets. As the reassure isn't yet officially accessible in territory China as of right now, examiners foresaw that to support this arrangement, Nintendo would need to discharge the comfort in China by 2019. Tencent is yet to remark with respect to a worldwide discharge, even after open examination.

Music

The amusement's music was formed by Hans Zimmer, Jeff Broadbent, Lorne Balfe, and Duncan Watt, and was performed and recorded by The Chamber Orchestra of London at Abbey Road Studios in London. A soundtrack collection was discharged on 28 October 2015. The all-encompassing soundtrack discharged in year two incorporates each unique occasion soundtrack since the amusement's discharge. Numerous score writers collaborated the collection including Howard Shore, Thomas Parish, and Marcin Przybyłowicz.

Addiction

On July 4, 2017, it was reported that the amusement proprietor's Tencent had endured lost \$14 billion, or 4.1%, on the Hong Kong Stock Exchange after the People's Daily censured Wangzhe Rongyao as "poison" for youngsters, calling the substance "a spot of qualities and historical perspectives" and addictive. Assortment named the two basic articles an "exhibition of the intensity of China's state-run media and publicity machine." Wangzhe Rongyao maker Lin Min a short time later noted online that the diversion's structure "completely consented to government necessities" and contended that "simply like different forms of amusement, recreations can be [a non-addictive] part of our normal day by day lives." In July 2017, Wangzhe Rongyao began constraining youngsters younger than 12 to one hour of play time every day. Youngsters matured 12 to 18 will be restricted to two hours diversion time for every day. Players under 12 will likewise be prohibited from playing the diversion after 9 pm. It is trusted that rising worries over intemperate gaming propensities in kids drove Tencent, the amusement proprietor, to self-force these limitations.

1.2 Purpose of the study

The purpose of this paper was to create and a test a model of a players' mobile game loyalty, particularly centering what factors comprise to loyalty towards a particular mobile game. From a theoretical viewpoint, there is an unmistakable need to construct a model that can help clarify loyalty in the mobile game. The model can fill in as a beginning stage for understanding mobile game loyalty by fusing flow theories and utilization and delights approach.

1.3 Research Significance

Thanks to rising incomes and increasing computer, smartphone, and internet access, China's digital game market has become the world's largest by revenue and number of consumers. According to market intelligence firm NewZoo, there are 575 million digital game consumers in China as of 2017. China's game market has grown quickly: from 2013 to 2017 the value of China's market has more than doubled from \$13.8 billion to \$32.5 billion. This research is based on a macro-level analysis; the objective is to express the customer satisfaction and loyalty on digital games in China. Moreover, a Chinese gaming studio Tencent will be used as a case study. I will look at the industry on a macro-level, but also give specific examples from the mobile gaming segment.

Mobile games are differentiated from other Platform games such as console, PC, and arcade games in terms of their portability, accessibility, networkability, and simplicity. Owing to the portability (i.e., mobility), users can play games anytime. This characteristic has attracted many light users, who play simple games such as puzzle, card, or word games because these games can be played in one's spare time in a short amount of time. Compared to players in other genres such as role-playing games (RPGs) and simulation games that require a long time to play, light users vary broadly in terms of age, and many women players also belong to this group. (Eui Jun Jeong & Dan J. Kim 2008). The Chinese mobile-game market has exploded, with revenue and that expansion should continue at a compound annual growth rate of 37.6 percent from 2013 to 2018. Key business performance factors for digital game organizations are the least addressed area in game development research. The business model for each segment of the game industry is different, and each segment has a different percentage of the revenue share. From a review of the literature, various factors have been identified that contribute to game business performance. The identified factors and the related literature review are described in the following sub-sections.

2.1 Loyalty

Loyalty is described as "a deeply held commitment to rebuy or re-patronize a preferred product/service consistently in the future, thereby causing repetitive same-brand or same brand-set purchasing, despite situational influences and marketing efforts having the potential to cause switching behavior". (Oliver, 1999) Consumers are theorized to become loyal following the cognition-affect-conation pattern and finally in a behavioral manner, which is described as "active inertia" or action loyalty. In the first loyalty phase, cognition can be based on prior knowledge or on recent experience-based information about the performance of the brand. Loyalty at the cognitive phase is focused on the brand attribute information available to the consumer. The second phase of loyalty development, effective loyalty, is directed toward the attractiveness of the brand, developed on the basis on previous satisfying usage occasions. The next phase of loyalty development, conative loyalty refers to a commitment to the intention to rebuy the brand. However, this desire may be only a "good intention", anticipated but without any realized purchase. In the action loyalty phase, the repurchase intention in the former state is transformed into an eagerness to act, accompanied by an additional will to overcome obstacles that might prevent the act. If the action is repeated, action inertia grows, therefore facilitating repurchase (Oliver, 1999).

Josiah Royce introduced an alternate meaning of the idea in his 1908 book *The Philosophy of Loyalty*. As indicated by Royce, loyalty is goodness, in fact, an essential idea, "the core of the considerable number of temperance, the focal obligation among every one of the obligations". Royce presents loyalty, which he characterizes finally, as the fundamental good guideline from which every single other rule can be inferred. The short definition that he gives of the thought is that loyalty is "the eager and useful and thoroughgoing commitment of an individual to a reason". Loyalty is thoroughgoing in that it isn't simply an easygoing interest yet a wholehearted promise to a reason.

Royce's perspective on loyalty was tested by Ladd in the article on "Loyalty" in the primary release of the *Macmillan Encyclopedia of Philosophy* (1967).

Ralls (1968) sees that Ladd's article is the *Macmillan Encyclopedia's* solitary article on excellence, and adulates it for its "grand" affirmation by Ladd that "a steadfast Nazi is a logical inconsistency in the wording". Ladd affirms that, as

opposed to Royce, causes to which one is faithful are relational, not unoriginal or suprapersonal. He expresses that Royce's view has "the moral imperfection of proposing obligations far beyond our individual obligations to men and gatherings of men. The individual is submerged and lost in this superperson for it will in general break up our particular obligations to others into 'superhuman' great". Ronald F. Duska, the Lamont Post Chair of Ethics and the Professions at The American College, broadens Ladd's complaint, saying that it is depravity of morals and excellence for one's self-will to be related to anything, as Royce would have it. Regardless of whether one was recognizing one's self-will with God, to be deserving of such loyalty God would need to be the summum bonum, the ideal sign of good.

Ladd himself describes loyalty as relational, i.e., a connection between a ruler and vassal, parent and youngster, or two great companions. Duska states that doing as such prompts an issue that Ladd disregards. Loyalty may surely be between two people, however, it might likewise be from an individual to a gathering of individuals. Instances of this, which are unequivocally viewed as occurrences of loyalty, will be loyalty by an individual to his or her family, to a group that the person in question is a part or devotee of, or to his or her nation. The issue with this that Duska recognizes is that it at that point ends up vague whether there is a strict relational relationship included, and whether Ladd's conflict that loyalty is relational—not suprapersonal—is a sufficient portrayal.

Ladd thinks about loyalty from two points of view: its legitimate article and its ethical esteem.

John Kleinig, an educator of reasoning at City University of New York, sees that throughout the years the thought has been treated by essayists from Aeschylus through John Galsworthy to Joseph Conrad, by analysts, therapists, sociologists, researchers of religion, political financial specialists, researchers of business and promoting, and—most especially—by political scholars, who manage it regarding loyalty pledges and energy. As a philosophical idea, loyalty was generally untreated by scholars until crafted by Josiah Royce, the "fantastic special case" in Kleinig's words.[8] John Ladd, teacher of rationality at Brown University, writing in the Macmillan Encyclopedia of Philosophy in 1967, sees that at that point the subject had gotten "meager consideration in philosophical writing". This he ascribed to "detestable" affiliations that the subject had with patriotism, including Nazism, and with the mysticism of vision, which he described as "out of date". In any case, he contended that such affiliations were flawed and that the thought of loyalty is "a basic fixing in any edified and another conscious arrangement of ethics". Kleinig sees that from the 1980s onwards, the subject picked up considerably, with scholars differently relating it to proficient morals, whistleblowing, kinship, and goodness hypothesis. Extra angles listed by Kleinig incorporate the exclusionary idea of loyalty and its subjects.

2.2 Customer loyalty

In the context of e-commerce, antecedents and consequences of customer loyalty have been investigated. According to Ribbink et al. (2004), trust in the electronic medium, known as "e-trust", and e-satisfaction both directly affect e-loyalty. Dimensions of e-service quality, such as assurance, ease of use; escape customization and responsiveness strongly affect satisfaction and indirectly influence e-loyalty. Srinivasan et al. (2002) concluded that seven factors, including customization, contact interactivity, care, community, cultivation, choice, and character impact e-loyalty. Their study also reveals that e-loyalty has an impact on two customer-related issues: word-of-mouth promotion and willingness to pay more.

The digital game industry (DGI) is facing dramatic changes because it views customer satisfaction as winning over players for their games. The classical definition of customer satisfaction given by Oliver is "pleasurable fulfillment response toward a good, service, benefit, or reward". Customer satisfaction must be an integral part of the organization and is a financial metric that can be used to measure business performance. However, the relationship between business performance and customer satisfaction is not always clear.

Zeithaml highlighted three problems in measuring this relationship: a) the time lag between measuring improvement in profit and customer satisfaction; b) other variables that influence an organization's profits, such as marketing, price, and competition; and c) other variables such as organizational behavioral issues that should be included when measuring the relationship. A positive relationship between customer satisfaction and organizational performance has

been reported by many researchers in different industries, but few have explored this relationship in the DGI. Some researchers have also highlighted that higher customer satisfaction in any organization is strongly correlated with higher market growth, proving the strong relationship between customer loyalty and customer retention. The DGI has given a lower priority to customer service for its product (the game) and tends to treat it as a commodity. Often, when players do not obtain a response to their problems, they become disappointed. Johnson explored the aspect of customer service in the DGI. He used the critical incidents technique to examine customer services incidents in the game industry and identified negative and positive customer service experiences. The results of this study provided directions for management that helped them with resource allocation, especially in those areas that provided maximum customer satisfaction and dissatisfaction. Based on this analysis, management could take proper measures to ensure maximum customer satisfaction. In commercial games, the concept of customer satisfaction has a very important place. Lu and Wang explored the factors of online game addiction and the role of addiction in online gamer loyalty and customer satisfaction. The results indicated that addiction plays an important role in customer loyalty and satisfaction. Wiele et al. investigated the relationship between customer satisfaction and business performance data within an organization. The results showed empirical evidence that there is a positive relationship between customer satisfaction and business performance. In the literature, only a few researchers have explored the customer satisfaction aspect of the DGI.

2.3 Loyalty in the mobile context

Lin and Wang (2005) examined the determinants of customer loyalty in mobile commerce context and found that perceived value, habit, trust and customer satisfaction are factors exerting significant influence in this subject matter. Their analysis successfully applied the traditional concept of customer loyalty in the mobile commerce context. In the mobile context, perceived enjoyment and perceived usefulness both play a significant role in influencing mobile loyalty. The impact of perceived enjoyment on loyalty may be more or less the same as that of perceived usefulness (Cyr, Head, & Ivanov, 2006). Results show that the incorporation of a hedonic component into the study of mobile loyalty is highly relevant and deserve researchers' attention. Wakefield and Whitten (2006) stated that perceived entertainment "is an intrinsic belief that is likely to maximize use of the device for users that expect immersing and playful interactions with the device". Properties or elements that raise cognitive absorption or playfulness will cause affirmative feelings that prompt usage behavior.

Because of serious challenge in the commercial center, organizations have expanded endeavors to actualize the client maintenance system so as to augment the lifetime estimation of clients (Boshoff and du Plessis, 2009). As indicated by Deng, Lu, Wei, Zhang (2010), client loyalty alludes to responsibility by clients to make reliable recurrent buys of a favored brand or administration notwithstanding situational and showcasing endeavors to impact exchanging conduct. For Cheng et al. (2011), consumer loyalty implies making and keeping up long haul associations with clients. Hong and Cho (2011) state that client loyalty shows the shoppers' mental connection to the item just as attitudinal promotion toward the business. Through fortified client loyalty, organizations can hold clients and, thusly, benefits increment (Lee, 2010). This agrees to a proposal by Deng et al. (2010) who called attention to that client loyalty is an indicator of long haul practicality of the firm as steadfast clients are not impacted by awful exposure and they give free verbal promoting and referrals. Cheng et al. (2011) suggested that it is savvy to keep up existing clients than getting new ones. To this the creators continued to express that the expense of building up another client is somewhere in the range of five and multiple times the expense of keeping up existing clients. This exhibits retailers need to hold faithful clients in light of the fact that, through cost-adequacy, there are high odds of survival and solid future development. As per Boshoff and du Plessis (2009), the advantages of client loyalty are that unwavering clients are shoddy to keep up, are cost inhumane, spread free positive verbal, dependably give proposals, and dependably attempt new items.

2.4 Uses and Gratifications theory

Uses and gratifications theory (UGT) is a way to deal with understanding why and how individuals effectively search out explicit media to fulfill explicit requirements. UGT is a crowd of people focused way to deal with understanding

mass correspondence. Wandering from other media impact hypotheses that question "what does media do to individuals?" UGT focuses on "what do individuals do with media?" It hypothesizes that media is a very accessible item and the crowds are the customers of a similar item.

This correspondence theory is positivistic in its methodology, situated in the socio-mental correspondence convention, and focuses on correspondence at the broad communications scale. The driving inquiry of UGT is: Why do individuals use media and what do they use them for? UGT talks about how clients intentionally pick media that will fulfill given needs and enable one to improve learning, unwinding, social connections/fraternity, redirection, or break.

It accepts that crowd individuals are not detached buyers of media. Or maybe, the crowd has control over their media utilization and accepts a functioning job in deciphering and coordinating media into their very own lives. In contrast to other hypothetical points of view, UGT considers that gatherings of people are in charge of picking media to meet their wants and needs to accomplish satisfaction. This theory would then infer that the media go up against other data hotspots for watchers' satisfaction.

UGT has a heuristic esteem today since it gives correspondence researchers a "point of view through which various thoughts and speculations about media decision, utilization, and even effect can be seen".

The origin of the uses and Gratifications (U&G) approach can be traced back to the 1940s when scholars in communication research field began to study why audiences engaged in different forms of media behavior (Ruggiero, 2000). The U&G approach reversed the conventional research agenda, changed the research question from "what do the media do to people?" to "what do people do with the media?", as noted by Elihu Katz (1959). It is proposed that media users search for a specific form of mass communication, such as the newspaper and the radio, to gratify their needs. If those needs are satisfied, people will probably reiterate the experience. Recently, researchers apply the U&G approach in the IS context to examine the audience experience associated with websites (Eighmey & McCord, 1998) and the motivations contributing to the use of social media (Raacke & Bonds-Raacke, 2008; Smock, Ellison, Lampe & Wohn, 2011). Dissimilar to motivation setting theory, encircling theory and preparing theory, this theory is about the utilization of media by people and not the impact of media. This theory is taken as the opposing theory to enchantment slug theory as this theory takes open to being dynamic while enchantment projectile accepts a group of onlookers as latent respondents. The theory is focused upon clients and group of onlookers approach. This theory is progressively identified with Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs.

Uses and satisfaction theory focuses on the choice of a gathering of people and is deterministic as media can be utilized in various ways and for various purposes. This theory expects that there is nothing like a flat out truth. The group of onlookers is said to have full command over the impact of media on them as the impact can be picked by the gathering of people themselves. The theory is firmly identified with human brain science of requirements, thought processes and impact.

Uses and gratifications approach

Mark Levy and Sven Windahl give a decent depiction of being a "functioning shopper" of media: "As generally comprehended by gratifications scientists, the expression "gathering of people action" proposes a voluntaristic and particular introduction by groups of onlookers toward the correspondence procedure. In a nutshell, it proposes that media use is propelled by requirements and objectives that are characterized by a group of onlooker's individuals themselves and that dynamic interest in the correspondence procedure may encourage, limit, or generally impact the gratifications and impacts related with an introduction. Current reasoning likewise recommends that gathering of people movement is best conceptualized as a variable develop, with groups of onlookers displaying changing sorts and degrees of action.

Assumptions of the theory

Not at all like different hypotheses concerning media utilization, has UGT given the purchaser capacity to perceive what media they devour, with the supposition that the shopper has a reasonable plan and use. This negates past

speculations, for example, mass society hypothesis, that expresses that individuals are powerless casualties of broad communications created by huge organizations; and individual contrasts point of view, which expresses that insight and confidence to a great extent drive a person's media decision.

Given these contrasting hypotheses, UGT is remarkable in its suspicions:

The gathering of people is dynamic and its media utilize is objective situated.

The activity in connecting need delight to a particular medium decision rests with the gathering of people part.

The media content with different assets for need fulfillment.

People have enough mindfulness of their media use, interests, and intentions to most likely furnish scientists with a precise image of that utilization.

Value decisions of media substance must be evaluated by the gathering of people.

Stages of the theory

Uses and gratifications hypothesis was created from various earlier correspondence speculations and research led by individual scholars.

Stage 1

In 1944, analysts started to investigate the most punctual types of uses and gratifications with their work characterizing the explanations behind why individuals picked explicit sorts of media. While analysts were considering, Herzog met different cleanser musical show fans and had the capacity to distinguish three kinds of gratifications. The three gratifications classes, in view of why individuals tuned in to cleanser musical dramas, were enthusiastic, unrealistic reasoning, and learning.

According to West and Turner, UGT was an expansion of Needs and Motivation Theory, as delineated by Abraham Maslow in 1954, which contends that individuals effectively hoped to fulfill their necessities dependent on a chain of importance. These requirements are sorted out as Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs as a pyramid with the biggest, most principal needs at the base and the requirement for self-completion at the best. From the base up the pyramid contains Biological/Physical, Security/Safety, Social/Belonging, Ego/Self-Respect and Self-completion at the best.

In 1954 Wilbur Schramm built up the division of determination, an equation for figuring out which type of broad communications an individual would choose. The recipe chose the measure of satisfaction an individual would hope to pick up from the medium over how much exertion they needed to make to accomplish delight.

Stage 2

In 1969 Jay Blumler and Denis McQuail contemplated the 1964 decision in the United Kingdom by analyzing individuals' thought processes in viewing certain political projects on TV. By arranging the gathering of people's thought processes to review a specific program, they planned to characterize watchers as per their requirements so as to understand any potential broad communications impacts. The group of onlookers inspirations they had the capacity to distinguish helped lay the preparation for their exploration in 1972 and in the end uses and gratifications hypothesis. In 1972 Denis McQuail, Jay Blumler and Joseph Brown recommended that the uses of various kinds of media could be gathered into 4 classifications. The four classifications were: preoccupation, individual connections, individual personality, and reconnaissance.

In 1973-74 McQuail, Blumler and Brown were joined by Elihu Katz, Michael Gurevitch and Hadassah Haas, in their media investigation. Community-Oriented research started to show how individuals saw broad communications.

Stage 3

The latest enthusiasm encompassing Uses and Gratifications Theory is the connection between the motivation behind why media is utilized and the accomplished satisfaction.

UGT scientists are building up the hypothesis to be increasingly prescient and informative by interfacing the necessities, objectives, advantages, and results of media utilization and use alongside individual variables.

Work in UGT was trailblazing on the grounds that the exploration of Katz, Blumler, and Gurevitch based on Herzog's examination and caused a change in outlook from how media impacts individuals to how crowds use media, decreasing the strength of the constrained impacts way to deal with broad communications think about.

In the 1980s, Rehman (1983) connected UGT to consider the connection between the motion picture gathering of people desires and fulfillment got from heading out to the films.

Present day uses of uses and gratifications theory

Cell phone utilization

Cell phones, a nearly new innovation, have numerous uses and gratifications appended to them. Because of their inclination of portability, consistent access, and alternatives to both include and access content, this field is expanding with new research on the inspirations driving utilizing cell phones.

All in all, individuals utilize cell phones for the accompanying uses and gratifications

Affection/friendliness

Entertainment

Instrumentality

Psychological consolation

Fashion/status

Mobility

Immediate get to

Uses and gratifications do, in any case, contrast dependent on area and gathering of people:

Using cell phones on transports, vehicles, and trains is identified with the UG of versatility and quick access

Talking to colleagues is identified with the UG of instrumentality

Talking to relatives is identified with the UG of versatility and fondness

The particular capacity of content informing has been concentrated to discover its uses and gratifications and investigate any potential sexual orientation contrasts. The scientists proposed seven uses and gratifications; they are recorded underneath, from most astounding to least positioned by the investigation's outcomes:

Accessibility/versatility

Relaxation

Escape

Entertainment

Information chasing

Coordination for business

Socialization/warmth chasing

Status looking

The outcomes additionally showed sex contrasts (in an undergrad populace): ladies scored the UG of availability/portability, unwinding and departure, and coordination higher than the men. These outcomes may infer social and societal desires for females around freedom however associated with family and companions and/or a propensity for ladies to depend more on an itemized discussion in content informing than men.

Since numerous currently utilize their cell phones as gadgets to associate with the web and both contribute and recover content, specialists have explored the UG of shrewd gadgets which draw in different media. The uses and gratifications for contributing versatile substance vary from those for recovering portable substance.

Contribution: Leisure, diversion, simple access, and hanging loose are altogether inspirations for including material.

Retrieval: Efficient access of data assets/administrations and the requirement for superb data are uses and gratifications for getting to content.

Internet usage

The Internet gives another and profound field for investigating UGT. It was found to have three principal classifications of gratifications: content delight, process satisfaction, and social delight.

Content: Uses for the Internet incorporate the requirement for investigating or discovering explicit data or material, which are delighted with substance.

Process: Users gain satisfaction from the experience of deliberate exploring or random perusing of the Internet in its useful procedure.

Social: Uses include a wide scope of framing and developing social ties.

Researchers like LaRose et al. use UGT to understand Internet use by means of a socio-subjective system to decrease vulnerabilities that emerge from homogenizing an Internet group of onlookers and clarifying media utilization as far as just positive results (gratifications). LaRose et al. made measures for self-viability and self-criticism and related UGT to negative results of online conduct (like Internet fixation) too.

Social media usage

An ongoing examination has seen long range interpersonal communication administrations, individual and subject-based web journals, and web gatherings set up together to consider the U&G in posting social substance, the connection among gratifications and narcissism, and the impacts of age on this relationship and these gratifications. Clients have inspirations of the accompanying generally:

Social and love

Need to vent negative emotions

Recognition

Entertainment

Cognitive requirements

Discussions were observed to be the primary media for venting negative emotions, conceivably because of the way that relatively, gatherings are to a greater extent a single direction road. Utilization of online networking fixes forlornness and fulfills an impulse for addictive practices. Like the factors of sexual orientation, area, and gathering of people as past research has discovered, the U&G varied by class of narcissism. The specialists discovered four multi-dimensional narcissistic identity types: feeling definitive or prevalent, exhibitionistic, exploitative, and frequently hungry for vanity. The U&G varied relying upon the particular kind of narcissism a given client had. For example, the individuals who were exhibitionistic would in general spotlight on the online networking U&G of appearing, communicating negative emotions, and perceiving. The individuals who saw themselves as unrivaled had higher uses and gratifications by intellectual inspirations than by acknowledgment. The vain narcissists were most delighted by acknowledgment and consideration, and they didn't vent negative sentiments.

Online gaming

This new part of research investigates the U&G of beginning to play recreations on the web. Accomplishment, delight, and social communication are for the most part inspirations for beginning to play a web-based diversion, and their prosperity at the amusement just as the degree to which their uses were satisfied anticipated their duration in playing.

2.5 Flow experience

The concept of flow was first introduced by Csikszentmihalyi (1975) in 1975. He specified it as "the holistic sensation that people feel when they act with total involvement". Flow is regarded as a multi-dimensional construct with several distinct components – control, attention, curiosity and intrinsic –interest. When people are in a state of flow, they are totally immersed into the activity; their attentions are centered to the activity itself; they feel in control of the environment and there is an enhanced state of sensory and cognitive curiosity (Agarwal & Karahanna, 2000). The key element in flow is that the activity itself must be autotelic, which means "people do it because they love it". There is no need for an external reward because the activity itself is intrinsically interesting and motivating (Csikszentmihalyi, 1975).

The theory of flow has been widely used in studying an extensive range of circumstances, including work, shopping, chess playing, rock climbing, dancing, and others. In recent times, researchers also applied flow in studying player enjoyment in online games (Hsu & Lu, 2004; Sweetser & Wyeth, 2005).

In constructive psychology, a flow state likewise referred to conversationally as being in the zone, is the psychological condition of activity in which an individual playing out an action is completely submerged in a sentiment of invigorated center, full inclusion, and delight during the time spent the action. Fundamentally, flow is described by total assimilation in what one does, and a subsequent misfortune in one's feeling of reality.

Named by Mihály Csíkszentmihályi in 1975, the idea has been generally alluded to over an assortment of fields (and is especially all around perceived in word related treatment), however the idea has existed for thousands of years under different names, prominently in some Eastern religions, for instance Buddhism.

The flow state imparts numerous attributes to hyper focus. Be that as it may, hyper focus isn't constantly depicted in a positive light. A few models incorporate spending "to an extreme" time playing computer games or getting diverted pleausurably consumed by one part of a task or undertaking to the hindrance of the general task.

Conclusion

The landscape of mobile gaming, particularly in China, represents a fiercely competitive yet immensely rewarding arena. This review article has explored the strategic positioning and challenges faced by Tencent, a dominant player in this dynamic market. Tencent's multifaceted approach, spanning mobile games, social networking, and online payments, underscores its commitment to innovation and customer engagement in a landscape where ideas are plentiful but successful execution is rare.

Through a comprehensive review of the literature, we have identified that the key to success in the mobile gaming industry lies in a deep understanding of consumer needs and preferences. Tencent's "Honour of Kings" serves as a prime example of how aligning game development with user expectations can lead to significant engagement and loyalty. This insight is crucial for mobile game developers aiming to thrive in an environment where the consumer's voice is louder and more influential than ever.

The importance of analytics in shaping the future of mobile gaming cannot be overstated. Every download, in-game action, and social share provides valuable data that, when analyzed effectively, can lead to improved game design, marketing strategies, and monetization models. The dominance of a few key players in the market, who have mastered the art of leveraging consumer data to their advantage, highlights the critical role of analytics in achieving commercial success and consumer satisfaction.

In conclusion, the mobile gaming industry, with its rapid pace of innovation and consumer-driven evolution, presents both challenges and opportunities. For companies like Tencent and others operating in this space, the path to sustained growth and market leadership is paved with customer-centric strategies, continuous innovation, and the effective use of data analytics. As the industry moves forward, understanding and adapting to the nuanced desires of the gaming community will be paramount for developers and publishers aiming to capture and retain the attention of players globally.

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References

- [1] Agarwal, R. & Karahanna, E. (2000) Time flies when you're having fun: cognitive absorption and beliefs about information technology. *MIS Quarterly*, 24(4), 665-694.
- [2] Ahuja, M.K. & Thatcher, J.B. (2005) Moving beyond intentions and toward the theory of trying: effects of the work environment and gender on post-adoption information technology use. *MIS Quarterly*, 29(3), 427-459.
- [3] Allen, N.J. & Meyer, J.P. (1990) The measurement and antecedents of affective, continuance and normative commitment to the organization. *Journal of Occupational Psychology*, 63(1), 1-18
- [4] Bhattacharjee, A. (2001) Understanding information systems continuance: an expectation-confirmation model. *MIS Quarterly*, 25(3), 351-370
- [5] Chin, W.W., Marcolin, B.L., & Newsted, P.R. (2003) A partial least squares latent variable modeling approach for measuring interaction effects: results from a Monte Carlo simulation study and an electronic-mail emotion/adoption study. *Information Systems Research*, 14(2), 189-217
- [6] Choi, D., & Kim, J. (2004) Why People Continue to Play Online Games: In Search of Critical Design Factors to Increase Customer Loyalty to Online Contents. *Cyberpsychology and Behavior*, 7(1), 11-24
- [7] Crosby, L.A., Evans, K.R., & Cowles, D. (1990) Relationship quality in services selling: an interpersonal influence perspective. *Journal of Marketing*, 54(3), 68-81.
- [8] Csikszentmihalyi, M. (1975) *Beyond Boredom and Anxiety*. San Francisco, USA: Jossey-Bass
- [9] Cyr, D., Head, M., & Ivanov, A. (2006). Design aesthetics to m-loyalty in mobile commerce. *Information and Management*, 43(8), 950-963
- [10] Eighmey, J., & McCord, L. (1998) Adding Value in the Information Age: Uses and Gratifications of Sites on the World Wide Web. *Journal of Business Research*, 41(3), 187-194.
- [11] Fornell, C., & Larcker, D.F. (1981) Structural equation models with unobservable variables and measurement errors. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 18(3), 382-388
- [12] Gefen, D., & Straub, D.W. (1997) Gender differences in the perception and use of e-mail: an extension to the technology acceptance model. *MIS Quarterly*, 21(4), 389-400
- [13] Hirschman, E.C. (1983) Predictors of self-projection, fantasy fulfillment, and escapism. *The journal of social psychology*, 120(1), 63-76
- [14] Hsu, C.L. & Lu, H.P. (2004) Why do people play online games? An extended TAM with social influences and flow experience. *Information and Management*, 41(7), 853 – 868
- [15] Huang, L.Y. & Hsieh, Y.J. (2011) Predicting online game loyalty based on need gratification and experiential motives. *Internet Research*, 21(5), 581 – 598
- [16] Katz, Elihu. (1959) *Mass Communications Research and the Study of Popular Culture: An Editorial Note on a Possible Future for this Journal*. Departmental Papers (ASC), University of Pennsylvania
- [17] Lally, P., Van Jaarsveld, C.H.M., Potts, H.W.W. & Wardle, J. (2010) How are habits formed: Modeling habit formation in the real world. *European Journal of Social Psychology*, 40(6), 998-1009
- [18] Liang, T.P., Lai, H.J. & Ku, Y.C. (2006-7) Personalized Content Recommendation and User Satisfaction: Theoretical Synthesis and Empirical Findings. *Journal of Management Information Systems*, 23(3), 45-70.
- [19] Lin, H.H., & Wang, Y.S. (2005). An examination of the determinants of customer loyalty in mobile commerce contexts. *Information and Management*, 43(3), 271-282.
- [20] Morgan, R.M. & Hunt, S.D. (1994) The commitment-trust theory of relationship marketing. *Journal of Marketing*, 58(3), 20-38.
- [21] Oliver, R.L. (1999) Whence customer loyalty? *Journal of Marketing*, 63 Fundamental Issues and Directions for Marketing, 33-44.
- [22] paidcontent.org. (2011) App Publishers Rebel Against Apple. Google Offers A Solution? Retrieved February 16, 2011, from <http://paidcontent.org/2011/02/16/419-app-publishers-rebel-against-apple-google-offers-a-solution/>

- [23] Papacharissi, Z., & Mendelson, A. (2011). Toward a new(er) sociability: Uses, gratifications and social capital on Facebook. In S. Papathanassopoulos (Ed.), *Media perspectives for the 21st century* (pp. 212–230). New York: Routledge
- [24] Raacke, J., & Bonds-Raacke, J. (2008). MySpace and Facebook: Applying the uses and gratifications theory to exploring friend-networking sites. *CyberPsychology & Behavior*, 11(2), 169–174.
- [25] Ribbink, D., Allard, C.R.v.R., Liljander, V. & Streukens, S.(2004) Comfort your online customer: quality, trust, and loyalty on the internet. *Managing Service Quality*, 14(6), 446 – 456
- [26] Ruggiero, T.E. (2000) Uses and gratifications theory in the 21st century. *Mass Communication & Society*, 3(1), 3-37.
- [27] Seek Omega. (2012) Why 99.9% of All Mobile Games are Not Profitable: The 6 Things Mobile Game Developers Must Do to Survive. Retrieved February 28, 2012 from <http://www.seekomega.com/2012/02/why-99-9-of-all-mobile-games-are-not-profitable-the-6-things-mobile-game-developers-must-do-to-survive/>
- [28] Srinivasan, S.S., Anderson, R., & Ponnawolu, K. (2002) Customer loyalty in e-commerce: an exploration of its antecedents and consequences. *Journal of Retailing*, 78(1), 41–50
- [29] Stack Overflow. (2011). Real-time multiplayer game over mobile network? Retrieved May 2, 2011, from <http://stackoverflow.com/questions/5861009/realtime-multiplayer-game-over-mobile-network>
- [30] Sweetser, P. & Wyeth, P. (2005) GameFlow: A Model for Evaluating Player Enjoyment in Games. *Computers in Entertainment*, 3(3), 3-3
- [31] Wakefield, R.L. & Whitten, D. (2006) Mobile computing: a user study on hedonic/utilitarian mobile device usage. *European Journal of Information Systems* 15(3), 292-300.
- [32] Wang, Y.S., Tang, T.I. & Tang, J.T.E. (2001) An instrument for measuring customer satisfaction toward a web site that market digital products and services. *Journal of Electronic Commerce Research*, 2(3), 89-102.
- [33] Yahoo Finance. (2017). Number of Smartphones Around the World Top 2.7 Billion -- Projected to Double by 2023. Retrieved October 19, 2018.